

SHORT NOTES

IDENTIFICATION OF β -SITOSTEROL IN CHAKSU OIL

BY I. SEN GUPTA AND ERICH MOSETTIG

An unsaponifiable fraction from chaksu oil, obtained from the seeds of *Cassia absus*, Linn., has been reported previously by Gupta *et al.* (*Res. Bull. Panjab Univ.*, 1954, 48, 63). After repeated recrystallisations of this material it proved to contain (by U. V. spectrophotometry) about 1% of a steroidal 5:7-diene. Further purification was achieved by chromatography on aluminium oxide. The fraction eluted by petroleum ether consisted of a waxy substance. The main fractions were obtained by elution with a mixture of benzene-chloroform (60:40) and accounted for 92% of eluted material. Crystallisation from methanol gave a compound melting at 135-36°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -32°.5. The infra-red spectrum of the compound indicated a 5:6-unsaturated sterol. A part of this substance in xylene solution, mixed with an excess of maleic anhydride, was boiled under reflux for 12 hours whereby the 5:7-diene was removed (U. V. spectrum). The melting points and rotational values of the alcohol, thus purified, its acetate, benzoate and 3:5-dinitrobenzoate correspond to those of β -sitosterol (Wallis *et al.*, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1938, 2, 336, 341).

Procedure.—Melting points (uncorrected) were taken on a Kofler block. Rotations were measured in chloroform solutions (conc., approx. 1%). I. R. spectra were obtained with a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer, Model 21, in chloroform solutions.

β -Sitosterol.—A partially purified fraction of the unsaponifiable fraction (130 mg., m.p. 131-32°) was eluted from 4 g. of "Aluminum oxide Woelm" ("non-alkaline, almost neutral"). The fractions (a total of 3.2 mg.) eluted with petroleum ether consisted of a waxy material melting indefinitely from 50-58°. The main fractions (a total of 117.8 mg.) were obtained by elution with a 60:40 mixture of benzene and chloroform. The product was recrystallised twice from methanol, m.p. 135-36°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -32°.5 (Lit., m.p. 136.5-37.5°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -36°.6). $\lambda_{\text{max}}^{\text{DIOH}}$ 262, 270, 282, 292; ϵ 118, 160, 170, 100, corresponding to approx. 1% of 5:7-diene. (Found: C, 84.09; H, 11.72. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{48}O$: C, 83.98; H, 11.15%).

β -Sitosterol acetate was prepared in the usual manner with pyridine and acetic anhydride at 0°. Two recrystallisations from methanol gave a product melting at 127-28°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -39°.10 (Lit., m.p. 126-27°, $[\alpha]_D^{20}$ -42°). (Found: C, 81.95; H, 11.66. Calc. for $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$: C, 81.57; H, 11.47%).

β -Sitosterol benzoate was prepared by treating the above sterol (40 mg.) with pyridine (1 c.c.), benzoyl chloride (0.4 c.c.) and a drop of methanol at 0°. The compound obtained was recrystallised twice from a mixture of ethanol-ether,

m.p. 142-43°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} -14^\circ$. (Lit., m.p. 144-45°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} -14^\circ$). (Found: C, 83.4; H, 10.7. Calc. for $C_{28}H_{34}O_2$: C, 83.34; H, 10.49%).

β -Sitoseryl 3:5-dinitrobenzoate was recrystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum (40-60°) and finally from a mixture of methanol-chloroform. m.p. 201-202° (Lit., m.p. 202-203°).

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CHEMISTRY OF MONOFLUOROTRIOXIODATES

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Although the two fluorides of iodine, IF_5 and IF_7 , have been well established, the only salt of complex fluoride anion isolated is KIF_6 (Emelius and Sharpe, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 2206). Compounds of IF_6^- ion have not been reported (Schumb and Lynch, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1950, 42, 1383). The oxyfluoro anion, $IO_2F_2^-$, has been known for some time and its chemistry including an investigation of the crystal structure of its potassium salt has been studied by Helmholtz and Rogers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 62, 1537).

After the isolation of monofluorochlorates (Mitra and Ray, *Science & Culture*, 1956, 21, 379), it was thought desirable to attempt the preparation of monofluorotrioxiodates. The present note, which is in continuation of investigations on the chemistry of oxyfluoride anions (Mitra *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, 22, 119; 1955, 20, 351, 404; 1953, 19, 216) deals with the chemistry of monofluorotrioxiodates. It is of interest to note in this connection that the anhydride, IO_2F , of the hypothetical acid, H_2IO_2F , has also been reported recently (Schmeisser and Lange, *Angew. Chem.*, 1955, 67, 156).

Method of Preparation.—The monofluorotrioxiodates of metals such as Zn, Ni, etc., have been prepared. The method of preparation is the same as that adopted for the preparation of other oxyfluoride anions. Equimolecular quantities of iodic acid (HIO_3), the metal fluoride (MF_2) and the freshly precipitated metallic hydroxide $\text{M}(\text{OH})_2$ were placed in a platinum basin containing about 60 c.c. of water. These were digested at about 80° for approximately 30 minutes on a water-bath. Glacial acetic acid was then added a little at a time. Within 20 minutes nearly all of the solid dissolved, forming a turbid solution which was filtered and allowed to stand in a vacuum desiccator (H_2SO_4). The highly soluble monofluoriodates crystallised out after a few days.

It was noticed that the addition of excess of fluoride, either in the form of the metallic fluoride or of hydrofluoric acid, resulted in the formation of difluorodioxiodate anion. This was therefore carefully avoided. The monofluorotrioxiodates of the bivalent metals such as Zn, Ni, etc. are, however, much less soluble than the corresponding difluorodioxiodates.

Zinc monofluorotrioxiodate has been isolated in the pure crystalline form. (Found: Zn, 17.39; I, 34.18; F, 4.88. $\text{ZnIO}_2\text{F} \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Zn, 17.8; I, 34.56; F, 5.17%).

A complex as well as double salts of zinc with monofluorotrioxiodate anion has also been isolated. As expected, there was some resemblance between these compounds and the corresponding salts of monofluorotrioxochlorate anion. The investigation of the monofluorotrioxiodates is still in progress and a detailed report of the work will be published in due course.

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